

APPRAISAL OF THE ROLE OF PROCUREMENT FUNCTION ON ORGANIZATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN FEDERAL MINISTRY OF EDUCATION ABUJA, NIGERIA

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Department of Procurement Management, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18456874>

<p>Keyword: Organizational Efficiency, Procurement Function, Supplier Management, Strategic Sourcing, Disposal of Stock</p>	<p>Abstract: This study appraises the role of the procurement function on organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja, Nigeria, focusing on three key procurement constructs: disposal of stock, supplier management, and strategic sourcing. Cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study whose population was 144 staff that performs procurement related activities in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja, Nigeria. Census approach was adopted and 144 copies of structured questionnaire was administered to respondents within the ministry, while only 118 were retrieved. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics for personal attributes of respondents while regression analysis was used to achieve the study objective and t-values and p-values were used to test the study hypotheses. Findings revealed that supplier management had the highest contribution to organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.713$, $p = 0.000$), followed by disposal of stock ($\beta = 0.339$, $p = 0.002$) and strategic sourcing ($\beta = 0.307$, $p = 0.001$). The study concludes that strengthening procurement policies and supplier engagement strategies can significantly improve organizational efficiency in the ministry. It recommends continuous evaluation of procurement practices, increased adherence to regulatory standards, and enhanced capacity-building initiatives for procurement personnel. Future research should explore the impact of digital procurement systems on efficiency and the role of policy implementation in public sector procurement.</p>
--	---

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

1.0 INTRODUCTION

There is increasing concern about organizational efficiency globally. This is because of the need to optimize resource utilization, enhance service delivery, adapt to technological advancements, and maintain competitiveness in a rapidly evolving environment. In the midst of these, the procurement function has become imperative in today's global public sector due to increasing demands for accountability, transparency, cost-effectiveness, and responsiveness in service delivery. Across both developed and developing countries, one of the key challenges threatening organizational efficiency in the public sector is the mismanagement of financial and material resources often manifested in delayed projects, inflated costs, poor-quality service delivery, and inadequate public trust. Procurement functions, when strategically executed, hold the potential to address these inefficiencies by ensuring value-for-money, timely service provision, and prudent management of public resources (Adedeji et al., 2023; Obasa and Gado, 2022). In Nigeria, and particularly in education ministries, these inefficiencies have significantly hampered the delivery of educational infrastructure and services, underscoring the need to appraise procurement practices as a vehicle for enhancing organizational performance.

Procurement function encompasses the processes and activities involved in the

acquisition of goods, works, and services that enable an organization to achieve its strategic and operational objectives. The public procurement process consists of various functional components, including strategic sourcing, supplier management, and stock disposal, each contributing uniquely to organizational efficiency. Strategic sourcing refers to a structured and analytical approach to purchasing that focuses on long-term supplier relationships, market analysis, and cost optimization (Osei-Tutu et al., 2020). It ensures that procurement decisions are based not just on price but also on quality, reliability, and total value. Supplier management involves building and maintaining effective relationships with suppliers to ensure compliance, risk mitigation, and collaborative value creation (Obasa and Gado, 2022). Effective supplier management reduces supply chain disruptions and enhances service reliability. Stock disposal refers to the systematic process of identifying and removing obsolete, redundant, or surplus items from the inventory to free up space and capital, reduce maintenance costs, and prevent waste (Yusuf, 2023). Collectively, these procurement functions have the potential to enhance organizational efficiency by reducing costs, ensuring timely delivery, and improving public sector responsiveness.

S. A. Tyokosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 11 Issue: 1,

January, 2026

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajmaf/>

Organizational efficiency is an institution's ability to use its resources; financial, human, and material in a way that maximizes output while minimizing waste. It implies achieving intended goals with the least amount of input without compromising quality or public accountability. This study adopts three measures of organizational efficiency: cost efficiency, process efficiency, and resource utilization. Cost efficiency is the extent to which an organization minimizes expenditure while achieving desired results (Adedeji et al., 2023). Process efficiency pertains to the effectiveness and timeliness of operational procedures that support service delivery (Ogbu and Idoko, 2020). Resource utilization refers to the optimal use of available resources such as personnel, finances, and materials to achieve performance goals (Elujekwute, 2022). When procurement functions are strategically managed, they significantly contribute to all three dimensions by enhancing accountability, speeding up service delivery, and eliminating resource wastage.

In developed societies such as the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia, public procurement reforms have been implemented to improve organizational efficiency by adopting digital systems, enforcing supplier compliance, and ensuring transparency (Walker and Radnor, 2022). In these nations, procurement functions have become central to achieving performance

targets, with strategic sourcing, supplier evaluation, and inventory control integrated into broader policy and performance frameworks. In Asia, countries like Singapore and South Korea have deployed e-procurement platforms and robust supplier management systems to streamline public sector operations, while in Africa, nations such as Kenya and South Africa have made strides in reforming procurement systems to minimize leakages and enhance service delivery (Mutai and Odhiambo, 2020; Malinga and Modise, 2021).

In Nigeria, despite the enactment of the Public Procurement Act (2007) and formal adoption of global best practices, many ministries continue to grapple with procurement-related inefficiencies. The Federal Ministry of Education, for example, has adopted formal procurement functions, yet still contends with procurement delays, poor supplier engagement, and weak inventory management. These issues have led to suboptimal educational resource distribution and frequent project bottlenecks (Oke and Ajayi, 2021). Although various studies (e.g., Obasa and Gado, 2022; Yusuf, 2023) have explored procurement's effect on public sector performance, there is a notable absence of empirical studies focusing on how specific procurement functions such as stock disposal, supplier management, and strategic sourcing

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

enhance organizational efficiency within the context of Nigeria's federal education ministry.

This gap motivates the present study, which aims to appraise the procurement functions within the Federal Ministry of Education, Abuja, and determine how they influence the ministry's organizational efficiency. While global and regional insights have shown promising outcomes when procurement functions are effectively applied, the persistence of inefficiencies in Nigeria's education sector suggests a need for localized analysis. By narrowing the focus to procurement's functional components and linking them to defined efficiency outcomes, this study provides an evidence-based assessment that can inform policy reforms and capacity-building initiatives tailored to the peculiarities of the Nigerian public sector.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the theoretical framework, conceptual framework, review of related empirical studies and a summary of literatures reviewed.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 Resource based theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory originated from Edith Penrose's (1959) work, which conceptualized the firm as a coordinated

bundle of resources and emphasized effective resource management, diversification, and productive opportunities. Emerging from the Theory of the Growth of the Firm, RBV developed more fully in the 1980s and gained prominence in the 1990s through Jay Barney's contributions. RBV became a dominant paradigm in strategic management by explaining how internal organizational resources drive efficiency, performance, and sustainable competitive advantage. Unlike externally oriented approaches, RBV adopts an internally driven perspective, focusing on the strategic role of firm-specific resources.

2.1.2 Agency theory

Agency Theory was principally propounded by Michael C. Jensen and William H. Meckling in their seminal 1976 paper titled: "Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure." In this work, they explored the relationship between principals (owners/shareholders) and agents (managers/executives), highlighting conflicts of interest, agency costs, and the need for mechanisms to align both parties' goals. The theory is an agency model that deals with situations in which the principal is in position to induce the agent, to perform some task in the principal's interest, but not necessarily the agent's (Higgs, 2018). Various mechanisms may be used to align the interests of the agent with

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

those of the principal. In employment, employers (principal) may use piece rates/commissions, profit sharing, efficiency wages, performance measurement (including

financial statements), the agent posting a bond, or the threat of termination of employment to align worker interests with their own.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers Conceptualization, 2025.

2.2.1 Concept of procurement function

Procurement is the strategic process of acquiring goods, services, and works from external sources through purchase or contract. It includes identifying organizational needs, selecting suppliers, negotiating terms, contracting, and ensuring timely delivery of quality goods and services. Effective procurement seeks to secure value for money, manage risks, and foster strong supplier relationships to enhance organizational performance. The process involves demand forecasting, sourcing, contracting, and supplier management, all aimed at obtaining required

resources cost-effectively, minimizing risks, and supporting the achievement of organizational objectives.

2.2.2 Dimensions of procurement function

i. Disposal of stocks: Disposal’ is the act of derecognizing an asset that has reached the end of its useful life when no future economic benefits or service potential is further expected from its use. Assets of such nature must be disposed or boarded off either with the aim of producing some financial returns or decongesting the stores to make way for new items and products (Mensah, 2014).

i. Cost Efficiency: Cost efficiency pertains to an organization's capacity to minimize expenses while achieving its objectives. It ensures that financial resources are optimally allocated, preventing unnecessary spending and enhancing overall financial performance. In the public sector, cost efficiency involves delivering services effectively without incurring excessive costs, thereby maximizing taxpayer value (Walker, 2024).

ii. Process Efficiency: Process efficiency focuses on the seamless execution of procurement tasks with minimal delays and errors. It ensures that workflows are optimized, reducing redundancy and enhancing service delivery. In public administration, process efficiency involves streamlining operations to deliver services more effectively and responsively (Walker, 2024).

iii. Resource Utilization: Resource utilization emphasizes the effective allocation and management of financial, human, and material resources to achieve maximum productivity. It ensures that assets are used efficiently, preventing wastage and optimizing operational outcomes. In the public sector, effective resource utilization involves deploying available resources in a manner that maximizes public value and service delivery (Kenway, 2025).

2.2.5 Nexus between procurement function and organizational efficiency

A good procurement system is vital to an effective organization's supply chain system. The forerunner to system performance in meeting its intended goals in governmental and independent sector is characterized by adequate management of the procurement function. Best procurement practices improve efficiency and effectiveness of an organization which translates to an improvement of its overall performance. Generally, procurement practices such as supplier relationship management, ethical procurement, information sharing, adoption of technology and adopting green supply chain management ensures that organizational performance is enhanced by supporting procurement functions in construction firms (Turban et al., 2018).

2.3 Review of Related Empirical Studies

Aputo (2024) examined the effect of procurement functions on project performance in Nairobi NGOs using a descriptive design. Surveying 76 NGOs, the study found that need assessment, sourcing, and contract management significantly influence performance. It concluded that procurement functions positively impact project success but failed to address organizational efficiency.

Adda (2024) investigated the relationship between procurement strategies and

organizational performance in Ghanaian industrial firms. Using Structural Equation Modeling, the study revealed that strategic practices like supplier relationship and risk management significantly enhance performance. However, the research was limited to the Greater Accra region, restricting the generalizability of findings.

Olowu (2024) assessed how procurement practices affect organizational efficiency in Nigeria's public sector using a quantitative survey. The study found that transparent bidding, strategic sourcing, and contract management significantly improve efficiency. However, it focused only on procurement officers, excluding other stakeholders like end-users, which limits the holistic perspective.

Ngwili and Were (2024) examined factors influencing procurement efficiency within Kenya's public institutions using a descriptive design. Targeting the Supplies Branch, the study found that stock disposal, ICT, staff competencies, and legal frameworks positively affect efficiency. However, the research did not explore specific procurement dimensions covered in current studies.

Oyuke and Shale (2024) investigated strategic procurement practices at the Kenya National Audit Office. Analyzing data via SPSS, the study found that practices like cost management, supplier relationships, and IT integration

significantly impact organizational performance. The study focused on Kenya, leaving room for exploration within the Nigerian public sector.

Wamae (2024) explored procurement functions in devolved governments using Machakos County. A regression analysis of 80 staff members revealed that procurement variables positively influence performance, with supplier management being the most significant predictor. The study noted that large sample sizes pose data handling challenges, addressed by this study's smaller sample.

Mugisha and Mwai (2023) investigated how procurement practices influence operational performance in Uganda's public health sector. Surveying 200 officers, the study found that planning and supplier selection improve service delivery. However, the regional and sector-specific focus means the findings may not be directly applicable to other countries or sectors.

Bediako and Appiah (2023) examined procurement governance in Ghanaian public universities using mixed methods. The study concluded that robust governance structures improve transparency and effectiveness. However, limitations include a small sample size of 150 and a failure to investigate specific barriers universities face when implementing these governance frameworks.

Oladeji and Aluko (2023) studied the impact of procurement practices on financial

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

accountability in five Nigerian local governments. Using secondary data, the study found that effective controls reduce mismanagement. However, the small sample size and reliance on documents limit the representation of broader challenges faced by procurement officers.

Adeleke and Adeyemi (2023) investigated procurement functions' impact on efficiency in Nigerian federal ministries. Surveying 120 officers, the study concluded that e-procurement and strategic sourcing significantly enhance efficiency. However, the sample size was deemed inadequate to represent the ministry's diversity, prompting the current study to focus on a single ministry.

Chinonso and Wanjiku (2023) examined procurement functions in Kenya's county governments. A cross-sectional survey of 100 officers revealed that training and transparent supplier selection significantly improve efficiency and reduce fraud. The study highlighted training's importance but failed to consider practices such as stock disposal and strategic sourcing.

Zwingina et al. (2022) examined procurement management's impact on Nigeria's oil and gas industry. Using an ex-post survey of financial statements, they found a positive but insignificant relationship between procurement and performance. However, the reliance on

secondary data prevented respondents from sharing their views on the study variables.

Obasa and Gado (2022) analyzed procurement functions at the Bureau of Public Procurement in Abuja. Regression analysis indicated that contract review and supplier choice positively impact performance, while contract monitoring does not. The study's limitation lies in its specific focus, restricting generalizability to the Federal Ministry of Education.

Adamu et al. (2021) analyzed procurement practices in Ghana's Assemblies. Surveying 113 respondents, the study found that planning, sourcing, and contract management positively link with organizational efficiency. However, the study did not cover the Federal Ministry of Education in Abuja, leaving a gap that the current study addresses.

Mpuone et al. (2020) explored the correlation between procurement functions and business performance in Nigeria's oil and gas industry. Using a correlation design, the study found that supplier management and strategic sourcing significantly correlate with market share and sales growth. The sector-specific focus allows this study to cover the Education Ministry.

Wambua and Kagiri (2019) investigated procurement practices at Oracle Technology Kenya. Surveying 500 procurement staff, the study found that risk management, partnerships, and ICT positively influence organizational

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

performance. Despite covering substantial ground, the study failed to address the disposal of stocks, which is included in the current research.

Mostafa et al. (2019) examined procurement practices in the service sector using an exploratory design. The study analyzed variables like customer orientation, IT adoption, and reverse logistics, finding a significant relationship with organizational performance. However, the research did not capture the effect of these variables on organizational efficiency.

Akubuko et al. (2019) studied how procurement management impacts vendors' performance in Rivers State's oil firms. Using chi-square analysis, the study found a significant relationship between procurement functions and vendor quality and profitability. The focus on the oil and gas sector limits generalizability to the Federal Ministry of Education.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model specification

In this study organizational efficiency (ORE) is regarded as a function of procurement function (PRF). The implicit form of the model is specified as follows:

$$\text{ORE} = f(\text{PRF}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{ORE} = f(\text{DS}, \text{SM}, \text{SS}) + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Thus, the explicit form of the model for this study will be as follows:

$$\text{ORE} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{DS} + \beta_2 \text{SM} + \beta_3 \text{SS} + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Where;

ORE= Organisational Efficiency

PRF = Procurement Function

DS = Disposal of Stocks

SM= Supplier Management

SS = Strategic Sourcing

α = Intercept of the Model (constant)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Parameters of DS, SM and SS respectively.

ε = error term

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

This subsection of the study presented the response rate, and analysis of demographic attributes of respondents, followed by analysis of the views of respondents to research instruments which the four variables of the study as captured by the research instrument.

4.1.1 Response rate

The response rate in a survey study is a pivotal indicator of the reliability and representativeness of the data collected. In this study, as presented in Table 4, the study distributed a total of 139 copies of questionnaires to respondents within the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja to gather data on the effect of procurement functions on organizational efficiency. Out of the total questionnaires issued, 118 were successfully returned, representing a response rate of 84.9%. However, 21 questionnaires were not returned, accounting for 15.1% of the total distributed.

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Table 4: Questionnaire Response Rate

Research Instrument	Sample	Percent (%)
Total issued out	139	100
Number returned	118	84.9
Number not returned	21	15.1

Source: Field Survey, 2025

4.1.2 Demographic attributes of respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents provides crucial insights into the composition of the workforce involved in procurement functions within the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. Understanding the age distribution, educational attainment, and years of experience of respondents is vital in assessing how these factors may influence procurement decision-making and overall organizational efficiency. Table 5 presents the demographic attributes of the 118 respondents who participated in the study.

The distribution of respondents by age indicates that the largest group falls within the 28–37 years category, accounting for 42.4% (50 respondents). This is followed by those aged 38–47 years, representing 29.7% (35 respondents). Employees between 48–60 years constitute 22.9% (27 respondents), while the youngest group, aged 18–27 years, and makes up only 5.0% (6 respondents). The predominance of respondents aged 28 years and above suggests

that most of the personnel involved in procurement activities within the Ministry have substantial professional experience and are at the peak of their careers. This ensures that their responses are based on practical insights rather than theoretical assumptions. The smaller percentage of younger employees suggests that procurement functions within the Ministry are largely handled by experienced personnel, which may contribute to stability but could also indicate a slower adaptation to modern procurement technologies and innovations. The respondents' educational qualifications reveal that the majority, 64.4% (76 respondents), hold an HND/Degree, while 26.3% (31 respondents) have Postgraduate Degrees. A smaller proportion, 9.3% (11 respondents), possess an OND/NCE qualification. This high level of education among the respondents suggests that the procurement staff at the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja are academically equipped to handle complex procurement tasks, including supplier management, stock disposal, and strategic

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 11 Issue: 1,

January, 2026

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajmaf/>

sourcing. The significant percentage of postgraduate degree holders further implies that a portion of the workforce has acquired specialized knowledge in areas such as supply chain management, procurement law, and strategic purchasing, which can contribute positively to the Ministry's efficiency.

The respondents' work experience is distributed as follows: 54.2% (64 respondents) have 16–25 years of experience, followed by 30.5% (36 respondents) with 1–15 years of experience, and 15.3% (18 respondents) with 25–35 years of experience. The fact that 69.5% of respondents have over 16 years of work experience suggests that the procurement function within the Ministry is managed by a highly experienced workforce. Employees with longer years of service are likely to have deep institutional knowledge about procurement policies, supplier relationships, and strategic sourcing methods. However, the relatively low representation of employees with fewer than 15 years of experience may raise concerns about succession planning and the infusion of fresh ideas and innovative procurement strategies.

By implication, the demographic attributes of the respondents provide a strong foundation for the credibility of this research. The high level of education and extensive work experience among procurement personnel within the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja indicates that the study is drawing insights from qualified and knowledgeable individuals. The age distribution confirms that procurement decisions are largely made by seasoned professionals who have witnessed procurement trends evolve over time. The educational qualifications ensure that respondents are well-versed in procurement principles, making their input highly relevant and informed. The work experience distribution suggests that the study benefits from insights based on practical, real-world procurement experiences rather than theoretical perspectives alone. Overall, these demographic factors reinforce the reliability of the study findings and provide a solid basis for evaluating the effect of stock disposal, supplier management, and strategic sourcing on organizational efficiency within the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja.

Table 5: Demographic Attributes of Respondents

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

18-27 years	6		5.0
28-37 years	50		42.4
38-47 years	35		29.7
48 – 60 years		27	22.9
Total	118		100
Educational Attainment			
OND/NCE	11		9.3
HND/Degree	76		64.4
Postgraduate Degrees		31	26.3
Total	118		100
Experience			
1-15 years	36		30.5
16-25 years		64	54.2
25-35 years	18		15.3
Total	118		100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

4.1.3 Analysis of respondents’ views to research instrument

This subsection discussed the answers provided by the respondents on the study variables which were grouped under four constructs: disposal of stocks, supplier management, strategic sourcing and organizational efficiency. The answers were provided on a five-point Likert scale showing the extent to which the respondents agreed and disagreed with the statements. These views are analysed subsequently as presented in Tables 6-9.

i. Analysis of Responses on Disposal of Stock

Table 6 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents’ answers regarding the disposal of stock in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The responses indicate that a majority of the respondents (82.2%) agreed that the ministry has a well-documented policy for stock disposal. Specifically, 45 respondents (38.1%) strongly agreed, and 52 respondents (44.1%) agreed. A small proportion of respondents, 8 (6.8%), remained undecided, while 10 respondents (8.5%) disagreed, and 3 respondents (2.5%) strongly disagreed. These results suggest that while most employees recognize a structured disposal policy, a minority

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

may be unaware of it or find it ineffective in practice.

Regarding the consistent application of disposal procedures across departments, 40 respondents (33.9%) strongly agreed, while 55 respondents (46.6%) agreed, making up a total of 80.5%. However, 10 respondents (8.5%) were undecided, while 9 (7.6%) disagreed, and 4 (3.4%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that although the majority believe stock disposal procedures are consistently followed, some employees perceive inconsistencies in their enforcement.

In terms of compliance with regulatory guidelines for obsolete item disposal, 47 respondents (39.8%) strongly agreed, and 50 respondents (42.4%) agreed, representing a total of 82.2% in agreement. Meanwhile, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 5 respondents (4.2%) strongly disagreed. These results reinforce that compliance with regulations is widely acknowledged, but some respondents might have concerns regarding full adherence or enforcement.

Lastly, responses to the periodic review of stock disposal methods also show strong agreement, with 43 respondents (36.4%) strongly agreeing and 53 respondents (44.9%) agreeing, making up 81.3% in total. However, 9 respondents (7.6%) were undecided, 8 (6.8%) disagreed, and 5 (4.2%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that while periodic reviews are largely recognized, a small proportion of employees may not perceive noticeable improvements from these evaluations.

The findings indicate that stock disposal practices in the ministry are generally well-documented, consistently followed, and periodically reviewed, with strong compliance with regulatory guidelines. However, the presence of disagreements and undecided responses (ranging from 10% to 15% in each question) suggests potential gaps in awareness, execution, or monitoring of stock disposal policies. To enhance the effectiveness of stock disposal practices, the ministry may need to conduct training sessions, improve communication of disposal procedures, and strengthen compliance mechanisms to ensure full adherence across all departments.

Table 6: Response to questions on disposal of stocks

Statement	Responses				
	SA(%)	A(%)	U(%)	D(%)	SD(%)

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

The ministry has a well-documented policy for stock disposal.	45(38.1)	52(44.1)	8 (6.8)	10 (8.5)	3 (2.5)
Stock disposal procedures are consistently followed across departments.	40(33.9)	55(46.6)	10(8.5)	9 (7.6)	4 (3.4)
Disposal of obsolete items is conducted in compliance with regulatory guidelines.	47 (39.8)	50(42.4)	7 (5.9)	9(7.6)	5 (4.2)
Stock disposal methods are reviewed periodically for effectiveness	43 (36.4)	53(44.9)	9 (7.6)	8 (6.8)	5 (4.2)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

ii. Analysis of Responses on Supplier Management

Table 7 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents’ answers regarding supplier management in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The responses indicate that a majority of the respondents (83.1%) agreed that the ministry maintains an updated database of approved suppliers. Specifically, 50 respondents (42.4%) strongly agreed, and 48 respondents (40.7%) agreed. However, 6 respondents (5.1%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 5 respondents (4.2%) strongly disagreed. These results suggest that while the supplier database is perceived as comprehensive,

a small proportion of respondents may have concerns about its accuracy or accessibility. Regarding the existence of clear criteria for evaluating supplier performance, 47 respondents (39.8%) strongly agreed, while 49 respondents (41.5%) agreed, making up a total of 81.3% in agreement. However, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 7 respondents (5.9%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that while formal evaluation criteria are widely acknowledged, there might be inconsistencies in their application or awareness gaps among staff. For the regular engagement with suppliers to discuss contract terms, 45 respondents (38.1%)

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

strongly agreed, and 51 respondents (43.2%) agreed, representing a total of 81.3% agreement. Meanwhile, 8 respondents (6.8%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 5 respondents (4.2%) strongly disagreed. These findings suggest that supplier engagement is generally practiced, but a small fraction of employees may not perceive it as consistent or effective.

Responses regarding predefined quality and delivery standards for suppliers indicate the highest level of agreement, with 53 respondents (44.9%) strongly agreeing, and 47 respondents (39.8%) agreeing, making up 84.7% in total. However, 5 respondents (4.2%) were undecided,

while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 5 respondents (4.2%) strongly disagreed. These findings suggest that quality and delivery standards are well-established in the ministry’s procurement processes, though a minority may have experienced lapses in enforcement or compliance. The findings indicate that the supplier management practices in the ministry are generally strong, with clear documentation, regular engagement, and predefined performance evaluation criteria. However, the presence of some undecided and disagreeing responses (ranging from 10% to 15%) suggests potential areas for improvement.

Table 7: Response to questions on supplier management

Statement	Responses				
	SA(%)	A(%)	U(%)	D(%)	SD(%)
The ministry maintains an updated database of approved suppliers.	50 (42.4)	48 (40.7)	6 (5.1)	9 (7.6)	5 (4.2)
There are clear criteria for evaluating supplier performance.	47(39.8)	49 (41.5)	7(5.9)	8 (6.8)	7(5.9)
The ministry regularly engages with suppliers to discuss contract terms.	45(38.1)	51(43.2)	8(6.8)	9 (7.6)	5 (4.2)

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Suppliers are required to meet predefined quality and delivery standards.	53(44.9)	47(39.8)	5(4.2)	8 (6.8)	5 (4.2)
---	----------	----------	--------	---------	---------

Source: Field Survey, 2025

iii. Analysis of Responses on Strategic Sourcing

Table 8 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents’ answers regarding strategic sourcing in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The responses show that a significant majority (82.2%) agree that the ministry conducts market research before selecting suppliers, with 52 respondents (44.1%) strongly agreeing and 45 respondents (38.1%) agreeing. However, 6 respondents (5.1%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 6 respondents (5.1%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that while market research is widely practiced, some respondents might perceive gaps in how effectively it is conducted.

Regarding whether strategic sourcing decisions are based on long-term procurement goals, 48 respondents (40.7%) strongly agreed, and 47 respondents (39.8%) agreed, making up 80.5% agreement. However, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 8 respondents (6.8%) strongly disagreed. These results indicate that while long-term procurement planning is prioritized, some respondents may feel that short-term

considerations sometimes override strategic goals. For the regular review of sourcing strategies to adapt to market changes, 50 respondents (42.4%) strongly agreed, and 46 respondents (39.0%) agreed, totaling 81.4% agreement. Meanwhile, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 6 respondents (5.1%) strongly disagreed. This finding suggests that while strategic sourcing reviews are practiced, there may be concerns about their frequency or effectiveness.

Finally, when asked whether cost, quality, and reliability are key considerations in sourcing decisions, 54 respondents (45.8%) strongly agreed, and 44 respondents (37.3%) agreed, totaling 83.1% agreement. Meanwhile, 6 respondents (5.1%) were undecided, while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 6 respondents (5.1%) strongly disagreed. These results confirm that procurement decisions prioritize essential factors, though a minority of respondents may have experienced instances where these principles were not strictly followed. The findings suggest that strategic sourcing is a well-implemented practice in the ministry, with a strong focus on market research, long-term

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

planning, and adaptability to market trends. However, the presence of some undecided and disagreeing responses (ranging from 10% to 15%)

suggests that there may be inconsistencies in implementation or communication gaps regarding procurement strategies.

Table 8: Response to questions on strategic sourcing

Statement	Responses				
	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)
The ministry conducts market research before selecting suppliers.	52(44.1)	45(38.1)	6 (5.1)	9 (7.6)	6 (5.1)
Strategic sourcing decisions are made based on long-term procurement goals.	48 (40.7)	47(39.8)	7 (5.9)	8 (6.8)	8 (6.8)
The ministry regularly reviews sourcing strategies to adapt to market changes.	50 (42.4)	46 (39. 0)	7 (5.9)	9 (7.6)	6 (5.1)
Cost, quality, and reliability are key considerations in sourcing decisions	54 (45.8)	44 (37.3)	6 (5.1)	8 (6.8)	6 (5.1)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

iv. Analysis of Responses on Organizational Efficiency

Table 9 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents’ answers regarding organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The responses indicate that a significant majority (80.5%) agree that the ministry operates within allocated procurement budgets, with 49 respondents (41.5%) strongly agreeing and 46 respondents (39.0%) agreeing. However, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 10 respondents (8.5%) disagreed, and 6

respondents (5.1%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that while budget discipline is generally observed, some respondents may have experienced budgetary overruns or inefficiencies.

Regarding whether financial resources are allocated efficiently across procurement needs, 52 respondents (44.1%) strongly agreed, and 45 respondents (38.1%) agreed, making up 82.2% agreement. However, 6 respondents (5.1%) were undecided, while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 7 respondents (5.9%) strongly

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

disagreed. These results suggest that while financial allocation is largely efficient, some respondents perceive gaps in how procurement priorities are addressed.

For the documentation and standardization of procurement processes, 50 respondents (42.4%) strongly agreed, and 44 respondents (37.3%) agreed, totaling 79.7% agreement. Meanwhile, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 8 respondents (6.8%) strongly disagreed. This suggests that although the ministry has structured procurement procedures, inconsistencies in documentation and adherence may exist.

When asked whether there are minimal delays in procurement request processing, 47 respondents (39.8%) strongly agreed, and 45 respondents (38.1%) agreed, totaling 77.9% agreement. However, 8 respondents (6.8%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 9 respondents (7.6%) strongly disagreed. These results imply that while procurement timelines are generally efficient, occasional delays are still a concern.

Regarding whether available resources are allocated based on educational priorities, 48 respondents (40.7%) strongly agreed, and 46

respondents (39.0%) agreed, totaling 79.7% agreement. Meanwhile, 6 respondents (5.1%) were undecided, while 9 respondents (7.6%) disagreed, and 9 respondents (7.6%) strongly disagreed. This indicates that while procurement is mostly aligned with educational priorities, there might be occasional misallocations or competing needs.

Finally, when asked whether the ministry ensures that procured items such as textbooks and equipment are effectively utilized, 51 respondents (43.2%) strongly agreed, and 44 respondents (37.3%) agreed, totaling 80.5% agreement. Meanwhile, 7 respondents (5.9%) were undecided, while 8 respondents (6.8%) disagreed, and 8 respondents (6.8%) strongly disagreed. These results suggest that resource utilization is largely efficient, although some respondents believe that certain items may not be fully utilized or effectively distributed.

The findings suggest that the ministry generally exhibits efficiency in procurement, financial resource allocation, and process standardization. However, the presence of undecided and disagreeing responses (ranging from 10% to 15%) indicates that some inefficiencies exist, particularly in budget adherence, procurement delays, and resource utilization.

Table 9: Response to questions on organizational efficiency

Statement	Responses				
	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

The ministry operates within allocated procurement budgets.	49 (41.5)	46 (39.0)	7 (5.9)	10 (8.5)	6 (5.1)
Financial resources are allocated efficiently across various procurement needs.	52 (44.1)	45 (38.1)	6 (5.1)	8(6.8)	7 (5.9)
Procurement processes in the ministry are clearly documented and standardized.	50 (42.4)	44 (37.3)	7 (5.9)	9 (7.6)	8 (6.8)
There are minimal delays in the processing of procurement requests.	47 (39.8)	45 (38.1)	8 (6.8)	9 (7.6)	9 (7.6)
Available resources in the ministry are allocated based on educational priorities.	48 (40.7)	46 (39.0)	6 (5.1)	9 (7.6)	9 (7.6)
The ministry ensures that procured items, such as textbooks and equipment, are utilized effectively.	51 (43.2)	44 (37.3)	7 (5.9)	8 (6.8)	8 (6.8)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

4.1.4 Regression Analysis

The study adopted multiple regression analysis to achieve the study objective of appraising the role of disposal of stocks, supplier management and strategic sourcing on organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The discussion of the regression results is done under model summary, analysis of variance and regression coefficients.

i. Model Summary

The model summary provides insight into the overall strength and explanatory power of the regression model in assessing the effect of the procurement function on organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The R value is 0.881, which indicates a strong positive correlation between the independent variables (disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing) and the dependent variable, organizational

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

efficiency. This suggests that changes in these procurement functions are closely associated with changes in organizational efficiency.

Furthermore, the R Square (R^2) value is 0.777, meaning that approximately 77.7% of the variation in organizational efficiency is explained by the three independent variables in the model.

This high percentage indicates that the procurement function plays a significant role in shaping the efficiency of the ministry's operations. The adjusted R Square is slightly lower at 0.770, accounting for the number of predictors in the model. This adjusted value confirms the model's reliability and its ability to generalize findings beyond the sampled data.

The standard error of the estimate, recorded as 5.400, represents the average deviation of actual

Table 10: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	R adjusted	square	Std. error of the estimate	Durbin Watson statistic
1	.881 ^a	.777	.770		5.400	1.979

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic sourcing, Supplier management, Disposal of stocks

b. Dependent Variable: Organisational efficiency

Source: Author's Computations using SPSS 2025.

ii. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) table evaluates the overall statistical significance of the regression model by determining whether the independent variables (disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing) collectively influence organizational efficiency in

organizational efficiency values from the predicted values In the model. A lower standard error typically suggests higher model accuracy. Lastly, the Durbin-Watson statistic, which is 1.979, falls within the acceptable range (1.5 to 2.5), indicating that there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. This confirms that the model's predictions are not influenced by patterns or trends that could distort its reliability.

Overall, the model summary suggests that procurement function dimensions (disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing) are strong determinants of organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja, making the regression model a good fit for analyzing their impact.

Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The regression sum of squares is 45.276, which represents the variation in organizational efficiency that is explained by the independent variables in the model. The residual sum of squares is 8.245, indicating the unexplained variation due to other factors not included in the

model. The total sum of squares is 53.521, which is the total variation in organizational efficiency. The relatively small residual sum of squares suggests that the model accounts for most of the variance in the dependent variable.

The mean square for regression is obtained by dividing the sum of squares by the degrees of freedom (df), resulting in 15.092. The mean square for residuals, which represents unexplained variance, is 0.072. The F-statistic, calculated as 209.610, indicates how well the independent variables explain the dependent variable compared to random variation. A high F-value suggests that the model is statistically

significant. The p-value (Sig.) is 0.000, which is below the conventional significance level of 0.05. This means that the overall regression model is highly significant, and there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis that the procurement function does not affect organizational efficiency. In summary, the ANOVA results confirm that disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing significantly contribute to organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The model’s ability to explain variations in efficiency is statistically valid, reinforcing the findings from the model summary.

Table 11: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	45.276	3	15.092	209.610	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.245	114	0.072		
	Total	53.521	117			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic sourcing, Supplier management, Disposal of stocks

b. Dependent Variable: Organisational efficiency

Source: Author’s Computations using SPSS 2025.

iii. Regression coefficients

The regression coefficients table provides insights into the individual contribution of each independent variable (disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing) to organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. It highlights their respective unstandardized and standardized coefficients, t-

values, and significance levels (p-values). The constant (Intercept) has a coefficient of -4.508, suggesting that if all three independent variables were absent or held at zero, organizational efficiency would be negative. However, since procurement activities are always in place, this value is not a primary concern but serves as a mathematical point of reference.

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

The unstandardized B coefficient for disposal of stocks is 0.228, meaning that for every unit increase in effective stock disposal, organizational efficiency increases by 0.228 units, holding other variables constant. The standardized β value is 0.339, indicating that disposal of stocks has a moderate influence on efficiency compared to other predictors. The t-value is 6.369, and the p-value is 0.002, which is below 0.05, indicating that disposal of stocks has a statistically significant effect on organizational efficiency.

The unstandardized B coefficient for supplier management is 0.556, meaning that a unit increase in effective supplier management improves organizational efficiency by 0.556 units, holding other variables constant. The standardized β value is 0.713, the highest among the three variables, indicating that supplier management has the most substantial effect on organizational efficiency. The t-value is 14.726, and the p-value is 0.000, confirming that supplier management is statistically significant in enhancing organizational efficiency.

The unstandardized B coefficient for strategic sourcing is 0.271, meaning that for every unit increase in strategic sourcing activities, organizational efficiency improves by 0.271 units, holding other variables constant. The

standardized β value is 0.307, indicating that strategic sourcing has a smaller but still significant effect compared to supplier management. The t-value is 6.994, and the p-value is 0.001, demonstrating that strategic sourcing has a statistically significant impact on organizational efficiency.

The regression results show that all three procurement dimensions (disposal of stocks, supplier management, and strategic sourcing) play a significant role in enhancing organizational efficiency. However, supplier management has the highest impact, as indicated by its highest standardized β value (0.713) and t-value (14.726). This suggests that effective management of suppliers, including selection, evaluation, and performance tracking, contributes the most to improving efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. Strategic sourcing and disposal of stocks also have positive and significant effects on organizational efficiency, but their impacts are relatively lower compared to supplier management. These findings emphasize the need for the Ministry to prioritize supplier management strategies, while also ensuring efficient disposal of obsolete stocks and enhancing strategic sourcing practices to maximize organizational efficiency.

Table 12: Regression Coefficients

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Model		Unstandardized coefficients (B)	Standardized coefficients (β)	t	P-Value
1	(Constant)	-4.508		-1.118	0.000
	Disposal of Stocks	.228	0.339	6.369	0.002
	Supplier Management	.556	0.713	14.726	0.000
	Strategic Sourcing	.271	0.307	6.994	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational efficiency

Source: Author’s Computations using SPSS 2025.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

The formulated hypotheses were tested using t-values and p-values in regression analysis, and the results are presented below.

i. Disposal of stock has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja.

The first hypothesis stated that disposal of stock has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. However, the regression results show that the coefficient for disposal of stock is $\beta = 0.339$, with a t-value of 6.369 and a p-value of 0.002. Since the p-value is less than the significance threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that disposal of stock plays a significant role in achieving organizational efficiency. Effective stock disposal minimizes wastage, optimizes inventory management, and enhances resource

utilization, thereby improving the efficiency of operations in the Ministry.

ii. Supplier management has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja.

The second hypothesis proposed that supplier management has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The regression results reveal that the coefficient for supplier management is $\beta = 0.713$, with a t-value of 14.726 and a p-value of 0.000. Given that the p-value is well below 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This confirms that supplier management has a significant impact on organizational efficiency. Strong supplier relationships ensure timely procurement, cost savings, and quality assurance, which contribute to improved efficiency in service delivery within the Ministry.

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

iii. Strategic Sourcing strategy has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja.

The third hypothesis suggested that strategic sourcing has no significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The regression output shows a coefficient for strategic sourcing of $\beta = 0.307$, a t-value of 6.994, and a p-value of 0.001. Since the p-value is below 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This result implies that strategic sourcing significantly influences organizational efficiency. By adopting strategic sourcing practices, the Ministry can secure better pricing, ensure the procurement of quality materials, and enhance long-term supplier partnerships, all of which contribute to operational efficiency.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This study sought to appraise the impact of the procurement function on organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. Specifically, it examined the role of disposal of stock, supplier management, and strategic sourcing in enhancing organizational efficiency. The regression results provide meaningful insights into how these procurement functions contribute to the Ministry's overall effectiveness. Each of these findings is discussed below.

i. The Role of Disposal of Stock on Organizational Efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja

The study examined whether the disposal of stock plays a significant role in achieving organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The regression results indicate that disposal of stock has a positive and significant effect on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.339$, $t = 6.369$, $p = 0.002$). This suggests that when obsolete or redundant stock is properly managed, the organization experiences improved efficiency.

The significance of stock disposal in the Ministry can be attributed to the fact that outdated or excess stock can occupy valuable space, increase storage costs, and lead to resource misallocation. By implementing an effective stock disposal system, the Ministry can reduce waste, optimize storage, and reallocate financial resources to more essential procurement needs. However, compared to supplier management and strategic sourcing, the impact of stock disposal is relatively lower, indicating that while it plays a role, it is not the primary driver of efficiency. This could be due to the less frequent nature of stock disposal compared to supplier engagement and sourcing activities.

The implication of this finding is that the Ministry needs to establish a structured disposal policy to prevent the accumulation of obsolete

stock. This may involve regular auditing of inventory, categorization of outdated items, and the implementation of environmentally friendly disposal methods. Additionally, digital inventory management systems can be adopted to enhance stock monitoring and disposal planning.

From a theoretical perspective, this finding aligns with Resource-Based View Theory (RBV), which emphasizes the importance of efficiently managing organizational resources to improve performance. The disposal of obsolete stock ensures that only valuable and necessary resources are retained, thereby enhancing efficiency. Empirical studies also support this result. Recent finding by Adeleke and Adeyemi (2023) who investigated the impact of procurement function on procurement efficiency in Nigerian federal ministries found that disposal stocks significantly improved organizational efficiency. Aputo (2024) also indicated that stock disposal has an effect on Project Performance. Similarly, Oyuke and Shale (2014) revealed that strategic procurement practices particularly stocks disposal significantly impact organizational performance. Again, Ngwili and were (2024) examined the factors influencing the efficiency of the procurement function within public institutions in Kenya found that stock disposal positively influenced the procurement function's efficiency

ii. The Role of Supplier Management on Organizational Efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja

The study also sought to determine whether supplier management influences organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja. The regression results reveal that supplier management has the strongest positive effect on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.713$, $t = 14.726$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that efficient management of suppliers significantly enhances the Ministry's operational effectiveness. The high impact of supplier management can be attributed to the critical role supplier's play in the procurement process. Effective supplier management ensures that goods and services are delivered on time, within budget, and at the required quality standards. It also helps to mitigate procurement risks, improve supplier relationships, and enhance cost efficiency. Given that public sector organizations rely heavily on external suppliers, a structured supplier management approach is essential for minimizing procurement delays and contract breaches.

This finding has significant implications for the Ministry. To maximize efficiency, the Ministry should implement a comprehensive supplier evaluation framework to select and retain only reliable suppliers. Additionally, contract management practices should be strengthened to

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

ensure compliance with agreed terms and conditions. Procurement officers should also undergo regular training on supplier negotiation strategies to enhance their ability to manage supplier relationships effectively.

The result aligns with Agency Theory, which explains the relationship between an organization (the principal) and its suppliers (agents). Effective supplier management reduces agency problems such as poor contract performance, inflated costs, and service delivery failures. Several past studies support this finding. Wambua and Kagiri (2019) revealed that supplier management positively influence organizational performance. The finding also agrees with Mpuon et al. (2020) who found that supplier management has significant positive correlation with business performance dimensions such as market share, sales growth and demand forecasting in Nigerian oil and gas industry. Again, the study finding is supported by a recent study by Adda (2024) which revealed that strategic procurement practices such as supplier relationship management significantly enhance organizational performance. Similarly, Wamae (2024) revealed that procurement variables had a positive influence on performance and notably, supplier management emerged as the most significant predictor.

iii. The Role of Strategic Sourcing on Organizational Efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja

The study further examined the role of strategic sourcing in achieving organizational efficiency in the Ministry. The regression results show that strategic sourcing has a positive and significant effect on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.307$, $t = 6.994$, $p = 0.001$). This suggests that the adoption of strategic sourcing practices enhances procurement efficiency and contributes to overall organizational performance.

Strategic sourcing involves long-term supplier selection based on quality, reliability, and cost-effectiveness rather than short-term price considerations. The significant effect of strategic sourcing in this study indicates that procurement efficiency improves when organizations engage in structured and data-driven sourcing strategies. By developing long-term supplier partnerships, the Ministry can achieve cost savings, better service quality, and reduced procurement risks.

This finding has important implications for the Ministry. To optimize procurement efficiency, the Ministry should prioritize supplier selection based on long-term value rather than immediate cost savings. Procurement planning should also integrate data analytics and market research to identify the most suitable suppliers. Additionally, collaborative relationships with

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

suppliers should be encouraged to enhance long-term cost benefits and service reliability.

From a theoretical perspective, this result supports Resource-Based View Theory (RBV), which emphasizes that organizations should leverage their strategic resources such as sourcing strategies to gain a competitive advantage. Empirical studies also confirm the relevance of strategic sourcing in procurement efficiency. Adamu et al (2021) found that procurement functions including strategic sourcing have a substantial positive link with organizational efficiency. Similarly, this finding supports that of Obasa and Gado (2022) which states that robust procurement practices such as strategic sourcing are essential for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of public sector organizations in Nigeria. In another study, Olowu (2024) revealed that effective procurement practices, including, strategic sourcing and contract management, significantly improved organizational efficiency by reducing delays, optimizing costs, and minimizing waste. And lastly, the finding by Oladeji and Aluko (2023) who found that effective procurement function such as strategic sourcing improves organizational efficiency also supports this study's finding.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presented the concluding part of the thesis which comprised summary of findings, conclusion, recommendations and limitations of the study. The section also presented suggestions for future studies and contribution to knowledge.

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study appraised the role of procurement function in achieving organizational efficiency in the Federal Ministry of Education Abuja, focusing on disposal of stock, supplier management, and strategic sourcing. The regression analysis provided statistical evidence that all three variables significantly contribute to organizational efficiency, with varying levels of impact thus:

- i. Disposal of stock has a significant positive effect on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.339$, $t = 6.369$, $p = 0.002$). This indicates that effective stock disposal enhances efficiency by reducing waste, optimizing storage, and reallocating financial resources.
- ii. Supplier management has the strongest effect on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.713$, $t = 14.726$, $p = 0.000$). This suggests that structured supplier management practices significantly enhance procurement efficiency.
- iii. Strategic sourcing also has a positive and significant impact on organizational efficiency ($\beta = 0.307$, $t = 6.994$, $p = 0.001$). This implies that organizations that adopt long-term sourcing

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

strategies experience cost savings, better service quality, and improved operational effectiveness.

5.2 Conclusion

The findings of this study confirm that procurement functions (particularly supplier management, strategic sourcing, and stock disposal) play a critical role in enhancing organizational efficiency. Supplier management emerged as the most influential factor, emphasizing the importance of effective supplier evaluation and contract management. Disposal of stock also significantly contributed to efficiency, by preventing inefficiencies associated with obsolete or excess inventory. While strategic sourcing plays the least role, it remains essential for reinforcing the need for long-term procurement planning rather than short-term cost-based decisions. This study therefore concludes that procurement function plays a significant positive role in enhancing organizational efficiency in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja.

REFERENCES

Adamu, M., Gyamfi, K. and Billa, G. (2021). An analysis of the effect of procurement practices on public institutions: an examination of Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (mmdas) in the Ashanti region of Ghana. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 12(03):083–093.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i.** A formal inventory auditing system should be established in Federal Ministry of Education Abuja to prevent the accumulation of obsolete stock. Environmentally friendly and cost-effective disposal methods should be adopted to improve efficiency.
- ii.** The Federal Ministry of Education Abuja should develop a structured supplier evaluation system that prioritizes reliability, performance, and compliance. Regular supplier performance assessments should be conducted to enhance procurement efficiency.
- iii.** The Ministry should institutionalize strategic sourcing by adopting data-driven supplier analysis, long-term sourcing plans, and collaborative supplier relationships to enhance cost efficiency, reduce lead times, and ensure the consistent availability of quality goods and services.

Adda, G. (2024). Examining the relationship between procurement strategies and organizational performance of Ghanaian firms: How does strategic procurement drive organizational success? *Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 103-115.

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 11 Issue: 1,

January, 2026

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajmaf/>

- Adebayo, O. (2021). Procurement practices and public sector efficiency in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Policy Studies*, 13(3), 45-58.
- Adedeji, A., Raifu, I. A., and Nnamani, G. (2023). Transparency in the procurement process in Nigeria. Brookings Institution. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/imp-erative-of-human-resources-in-effective-public-procurement-challenges-and-prospects-in-nigeria/>
- Adeleke, T., and Adeyemi, M. (2023). The role of procurement functions in enhancing procurement efficiency in Nigerian federal ministries. *Journal of E-Government and Public Procurement*, 2(2), 65-78.
- Afolabi, A., Ibem, E., Aduwo, E., and Tunji-Olayeni, P. (2020). Digitizing the grey areas in the Nigerian public procurement system using eProcurement technologies, *International Journal of Construction Management*, DOI: 10.1080/15623599.2020.1774836.
- Agaba, E. and Shipman, N. (2015). Public Procurement Reform in Developing countries: The Ugandan Experience. Boca Raton, FL: Academics Press.
- Ahmed, A. M. (2019). Procurement Practices and Organizational Performance in Selected Telecommunication Industry in Hargeisa, Somaliland. Published MBA Thesis. Kampala International University, Uganda.
- Ajomo, S. (2019). Purchasing and Supply Management. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 1(6): 17-22.
- Akubuko, G. C., Obodo, N. A., Musa, Abdullai A., and Jimoh, A. (2019). A Re-appraisal of Procurement Management Practices and Vendor Performance: A Case of Oil Producing Firms in Rivers State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Social and Management Sciences*, 5(11).
- Akumuntu, J. (2019). A Study of Efficiency and Effectiveness of Procurement Processes and Performance. *International Journal of Research in Management, Economics and Commerce*, 09(5):1-9.
- Aleman, L. N., and Guererro, T. (2016). Good Procurement Practices and SMEs in Global Supply Chains. *Journal of*

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 11 Issue: 1,

January, 2026

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajmaf/>

Purchasing and Supply Management, 1(5): 18-26.

Nairobi County, Kenya. MBA Thesis, School of Business and Public Management KCA University.

Al-Shaiba A, Al-Ghamdi SG, Koç M. (2020). Measuring efficiency levels in Qatari organizations and causes of inefficiencies. *International Journal of Engineering Business Management*, 12.

Awuah, G., Anane, A. and Kakra, S. A. (2022). The Effect of procurement process on procurement performance of public tertiary institutions in Ghana. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 13(02):121–130.

Al-Shaiba, A.S., Al-Ghamdi, S.G., and Koc, M. (2019). Comparative review and analysis of organizational (in) efficiency indicators in Qatar. *Sustainability*, 11(2)6-17.

Ayoyi, I. R. and Odunga, R. (2015). Role of Strategic Sourcing on Public Procurement Performance in Kenya. *European Journal of Logistics, Purchasing and Supply Chain Management*, 3(4):1-8.

Ama, O., Tyungu, A., Udende, W. and Tiza, M. T. (2023). Enhancing procurement efficiency through strategic budgeting: A case study of Benue State Ministries, Departments, and Agencies (MDAs). *Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances*, 16(3):70–81.

Baidoo-Baiden, S. A. (2021). Role of Multi-Sourcing Strategies in Public Procurement in Ghana. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Educational Research (IJM CER)*, 3(6):100-106.

Aputo, S. L (2024). The effect of procurement functions on project performance in non-governmental organizations in Nairobi County, Kenya. A Master Degree thesis in the Department of administration School of Business and Public Management at KCA University.

Balaeva, O., Rodionova, Y., Yakovlev, A., and Tkachenko, A. (2021). Public procurement efficiency as perceived by market participants: The case of Russia. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 1–12.

Aputo, S. L. (2017). The Effect of Procurement Functions on Project Performance in Non-Governmental Organizations in

Bals, L., Schulze, H., Kelly, S., and Stek, K. (2019). Purchasing and supply

S. A. Tyoakosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev

Advance Journal of Management, Accounting and Finance

Adv. J. Man. Acc. Fin

Volume: 11 Issue: 1,

January, 2026

ISSN: 2364 – 4219

Impact Factor: 8.17

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/ajmaf/>

management (PSM) competencies: Current and future requirements. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 25(5):1–15.

Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1):99–120.

Basheka, B. C. (2021). Procurement Planning and Accountability of Local Government Procurement Systems in Developing Countries: Evidence from Uganda. *Journal of Public Procurement*, 8 (3), 379-406.

Batenburg, R., and Versendaal, J. (2016). E-Procurement: An overview of the

processes and practices. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 36(10), 1423-1442.

Bediako, A., and Appiah, K. (2023). The impact of procurement governance structures on organizational effectiveness in Ghana's public universities. *Journal of Procurement and Public Sector Management*, 10(3), 198-213.

Bernhold, T. and Wiesweg, N. (2021). Principal-Agent Theory: Perspectives and practices for effective workplace solutions. In book: *A Handbook of Management Theories and Models for Office Environments and Services*. Routledge. Pp. 117-128.

S. A. Tyokosu, Utsev Simon Terdue and Luper lorpev